

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**
[ISSN: 0975-4725; CODEN(USA): IJPS00]
Journal Homepage: <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>

Research Article

Community based Retrospective Study on Impact of Maternal Nutrition and Child health outcomes in Yallamanda & Nearby Villages of Narasaraopet

Dr. Shaik Farahan Subahan*, Dr. J. N. Suresh Kumar, Chimata Hanumantha Rao, Chuppana Naga Veera Durga Sai Madhurya, Dudekula Sajeedha, Gurrapusala Lakshmi Venkata Surekha, Sheik Nageena Bee

Narasaraopeta Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences.

ARTICLE INFO

Published: 31 Mar. 2025

Keywords:

Maternal Nutrition, Pregnancy Diet, Foetal Development, Cognitive Growth, Child Health, Birth Outcomes, Low Birth Weight, Preterm Birth, Maternal Well-Being, Pregnancy Outcomes.

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.15112837

ABSTRACT

The mother's physical & mental well-being during pregnancy has a big impact on the child's long-term development and health. The goal of this review is to present a thorough evaluation of the research on the relationship between healthy eating during pregnancy and the development of the foetus, taking into account aspects related to the physical, cognitive, emotional & social domain. During pregnancy a healthy nutrient-rich diet is essential for the foetal healthy growth & development. Good foetal organ development, cognitive function & immune system resilience are all supported by a diet rich in important macronutrients & micronutrients. Nutrition significantly influences child health during birth, with its effect evident in adverse outcomes immediately after delivery. These outcomes such as low birth weight, intrauterine growth retardation, and preterm birth, can have serious long-term health implications, including the risk of death. Furthermore, inadequate nutrition can hinder child growth, leading to stunting and long-lasting cognitive impairments. This research is necessary to understand how mother health, whether physical or mental, impacts the development of the child & how pregnancy precautions can further prevent it.

INTRODUCTION

Pregnancy is a special time in life that has the potential to have a significant impact on the health of the mother & her off springs. The health of

mothers & children is greatly influenced by nutrition, and dietary changes made during pregnancy can have an impact on the health of the mother, foetus, and new born. The primary factors that can either positively or negatively affect foetal

***Corresponding Author:** Dr. Shaik Farahan Subahan

Address: Narasaraopeta Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences.

Email ✉: chimatahanumantharao03@gmail.com

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

development include poor mother nutritional status, maternal body composition, metabolism & placental nutrient availability. These factors have been directly linked to unfavorable pregnancy outcomes and the manifestation or foetal genetic potential. By affecting the availability of methyl donors and mechanisms that promote DNA stability, macro and micronutrients directly regulate DNA stability and phenotypic adaptation. As a result, they act as substrates, transcription factors and gene expression modifiers, influencing intricate biological pathways involved in embryogenesis as well as fetal growth and development.^[1] Healthy babies with appropriate birth weight and organ development are more likely to be born to pregnant women who eat a balanced diet and gain between 10 to 12kg during their pregnancy. These babies are also less likely to suffer from infections morbidity and death, since most organs, including the brain, an infant's diet and nutrition are crucial, particularly during the first 2yrs of life. However, it's crucial to realize that a mother's nutritional status should be in good shape. Prior to becoming pregnant in order to achieve the desired weight gain as well as good health and nourishment during pregnancy. This is called pre-pregnancy nutrition. For this assess BMI or body Weight against Height, Hemoglobin status, BP, Thyroid status and Blood glucose levels. Furthermore, a woman must also be at least 21yrs old to be eligible for them.

Table 1: Recommended food groups and raw amounts (g/day) to meet dietary requirements of normal and undernourished pregnant women

Food groups	Malnourished Pregnant women [g/day (Kcal)]
Cereals and millets	260 (876)
Pulses and legumes	90 (290)
Nuts and oil seeds	40 (206)
Vegetables	200 (70)
Roots and tubers	100 (58)

Green leafy vegetables	150 (67)
Fruits	150 (80)
Egg	50 (74)
Milk	400 (288)
Fats and edible oils	20 (180)
Energy requirement	2120

First trimester: Nutrient- rich balanced diet must be consumed.

Second & third trimester: An additional 350 kcal must be added to nutrient- rich balance of diet as suggested but for under nutrition pregnant women on additional 100kcal per day is recommended to be added to meet the additional energy requirement.^[2]

Importance Of Nutrition

The significance of diet in as we progress towards globalization and modernization, the diet is growing. The environment is changing, necessitating adjustments and manipulations in dietary consumption. Adult women's nutritional status is extremely significant and has a major impact on a child's development.^[3] The mother's diet has a direct effect on the foetus, which in turn affects the health of the newborn and child.^[4] Numerous research on the relationship between maternal nutrition and birth outcomes have demonstrated that low birth weights, intrauterine growth retardation, preterm birth, and other birth outcomes might result from poor nutrition for mothers. The effects of a single diet (such as iodine, iron and several vitamins and minerals) on the health of mothers and children have been the subject of certain research.^[5] It has been assessed in variety of status is influenced by secondary factors. A person's nutritional status is determined by the following factors:

1. Demographic: age, sex, and place of residence
2. Biological: development and growth
3. Additional co-morbidities, if any

4. Socioeconomic: environment, knowledge, income, occupation (length and type), and lifestyle. Additionally, several studies have found that low-middle-income countries have the highest rates of dietary deficiencies, and that nutrition continues to be a major contributing factor to newborn facilities.^[6]

Impact Of Mother’s Nutrition During Pregnancy on Fetal Development

Pregnancy- related dietary health effects on fetal development maintaining a nutritious diet during pregnancy is essential. The growing fetus depends solely on the mother’s nutrition for the vitamins, minerals and other nutrients that are necessary for growth. The best possible development of the baby’s organs, brain, and immune system is guaranteed by a diet that is well-balanced and high

in nutrients. Women may suffer negative consequences if they are deficient in vital nutrients such as folic acid, iron, calcium, and omega-3 fatty acids. A balanced diet that includes vitamins, micronutrients, and macronutrients must be considered throughout pregnancy. Carbohydrates, proteins, and lipids are examples of macronutrients that sustain fetal growth and development and give off energy. Iron, calcium, and folate are micronutrients that are necessary for the development of red blood cells, bone growth, and the prevention of birth-related disabilities. Vitamin D and calcium absorption, while vitamin C promotes tissue repair and enhances the immune system, B-complex vitamin for metabolism and brain development, vitamin E for cell protection, and vitamin A for vision and cell growth are additional vital vitamins for expectant mothers.

Table 2: Highlights the suggested dietary allowances for pregnant women as well as the estimated average requirements and recommended dietary allowances for non-pregnant women.^[7]

Nutrient	Recommended dietary allowances, adult non-pregnant women	Estimated average requirements, pregnant women	Recommended dietary allowance pregnant women
Iron (mg/day)	18	22	27
Iodine (ug/day)	150	160	220
Calcium (mg/day)	1000	800	1000
Ascorbic acid (mg/day)	75	70	85
VitaminB ₁₂ (mg/day)	2.4	2.2	2.6
Calciferol (ug/day)	15	10	15
Retinol (ug/day)	700	550	770

Folic Acid

Particularly in the early stages, Folic acid is essential for healthy foetal development. It is essential for tissue formation, cell division, and the creation of De-oxyribose nucleic acids. Insufficient folic acid during pregnancy increases

the risk of neural tube abnormalities in the developing fetus. Spina bifida, anencephaly, and encephalocele are examples of severe brain and spinal cord abnormalities referred to as neural tube defects.^[8] Additionally, a lack of folic acid may disrupt the heart and cardiovascular system’s normal development, raising the child’s chance of

congenital heart abnormalities. Folic acid containing prenatal vitamins are frequently recommended to satisfy the elevated needs. Consuming foods high in folate, such as citrus fruits, green vegetables, legumes, and fortified grains, can also help avoid a child's folic acid deficiency and promote the development of their organs.^[9]

Iron

A mother pregnancy-related iron levels can have a big impact on how the baby's organs grow. Iron is a necessary element for the formation of hemoglobin, the protein found in red blood cells that carries oxygen throughout the body. Inadequate consumption of iron cause deficiency anemia in the mother, which lowers her ability to carry oxygen. For the brain to grow and develop properly, there must be an adequate amount of oxygen. An iron deficient in children may have cognitive and behavioral issues, including as a lower IQ, trouble paying attention, and trouble learning.^[10] Additionally, Iron is essential for the immune system, and a pregnancy iron deficient can impair the children impair the child's immune response, leaving them more vulnerable to illness and infections.^[11] To prevent these possible impacts on organ development, pregnant women need to consume adequate amount of iron. Foods high in iron, including lean meats, poultry, fish, legumes, fortified cereals, and dark leafy greens, can help you achieve your objectives^[12].

Vitamin D

Vitamin D is crucial for the growth of bones and teeth because it aids in the absorption of calcium and phosphorous, resulting in skeletal deformities such rickets, a condition characterized by weak and fragile bones.^[13] Vitamin D also has a role in immune system regulation in addition to bone health. Research has discovered correlations

between maternal vitamin D levels during pregnancy and an increased risk of childhood asthma, wheezing, and respiratory tract infections. There is evidence that maternal vitamin D deficiency may be linked to 20% of developmental delays in children.^[14] Pregnant women maintain adequate vitamin D levels to reduce these risks, which can be achieved through sunlight exposure, dietary sources (such as fatty fish, fortified dairy products, and eggs), and vitamin D supplements, as recommended by medical professionals. Getting enough vitamin D during pregnancy is crucial for fostering optimal brain development, a robust immune system, and general healthy growth and development in the child.^[15]

Vitamin B₁₂

Vitamin B₁₂ is necessary for the growth and the functioning of the neurological system, it is particularly important during pregnancy, when the neural tube and foetus brain are growing. It has been linked to a higher prevalence of neural tube abnormalities, such as spina bifida, and poor brain development, which may cause the child to acquire cognitive and neurological deficient.^[16] Additionally, a lack of vitamin B₁₂ during pregnancy has been connected to a higher risk of premature birth, poor birth weight and the child's developmental impairments. Meat, fish, dairy products, and fortified cereals are foods high in Vitamin B₁₂. Pregnant women should make sure they are getting enough Vitamin B₁₂ through a healthy diet and supplements to avoid these problems.^[17]

Iodine

Iodine thyroid hormone production, which is essential for brain development, might be hampered by inadequate iodine intake. Cognitive and neurological disadvantages, such as lower IQ, trouble collaborating with others, and issues with

memory and focus, can arise from this deficiency. An iodine deficiency raises the likelihood of hearing impairments, speech and language difficulties, and weakened immune systems, which makes children more susceptible to infections.^[18] Physical growth may also be impacted, resulting in shortened stature and decreased motor skills. Pregnant women should take a sufficient dose of iodine, perhaps 220-250 micrograms per day, to avoid adverse effects. It is advised to consume foods like iodized salt, shellfish, seaweed, avocados, dairy products, and eggs. Supplemental iodine may be required in some situations. The optimal development of the unborn child depends on maintaining a good and balanced diet throughout pregnancy.^[19]

METHODOLOGY

Study site: Yallamanda & Nearby villages at Narasaraopet

Study type: Retrospective study.

Study period: 4 months

Sample size: 230

Anthropometric measurements including maternal weight, height, body mass index, total weight gain in pregnancy and infants birth weight were recorded and all mothers were interviewed for their bio-social variables, previous history of prematurity or low birth weight, complications and illness during pregnancy, details of antenatal care, dietary routine, type of physical activity and any morbid and condition during and before pregnancy. Birth weight of the newborn, hemoglobin level of mother during and before pregnancy, pre-pregnancy weight and total maternal weight gain were sourced from community.

Inclusion Criteria:

1. Children aged 0-6 years.

2. Studies addressing populations with specific nutritional interventions, deficiencies (or) diverse dietary patterns.
3. Studies measuring physical growth, cognitive development, language, skills, motor abilities (or) behavioural outcomes.

Exclusion criteria:

1. Children beyond age 6 years.
2. Outcomes unrelated to child development (ex: disease incidence without a developmental link).

Plan of Work:

Phase 1:

1. Protocol Preparation
2. Obtain the IEC approval for study.
3. Detailed Literature review.
4. Procure the questionnaire.

Phase 2:

5. Selection of sample population.
6. Collection of data Analysis.

Phase 3:

7. Analysis of collected data by using Ms, Excel, SPSS (Statistical Package fo the Social Sciences).

Statistics / Data analysis:

Descriptive analysis of data using different statistical tools, MS excel has been used for statistical analysis.

Data collection:

The data was collected from the mothers about their nutritional status during pregnancy. The collected data included the demographic details like name, age, gender, height, weight of the

children and pregnancy data of the mother about the food taken during pregnancy, complications arise during pregnancy like Miscarriage, Preterm delivery, Gestational diabetes, Gestational BP, Thyroid, Anemia, Eclampsia, Hydramnios, Pregnancy under 18, term of the delivery and nutritional status. From the height and weight of the child BMI will be calculated to assess whether the child is underweight/ overweight/ healthy weight, as the nutrition may impact the BMI.

Follow up procedures:

The data was collected from the community settings of Narasaraopet and near localities and

collected information from the mothers of the child about their nutritional status during pregnancy and after child birth and some of the data was collected from the ANM. We have visited the community for the collection of data during every Thursday and Friday in a week for a particular time provided to us.

RESULTS

Table 3: Mode of Delivery Distribution

Mode of Delivery	No. of Deliveries (n=230)	Percentage (%)
Normal	37	16%
Caesarian	193	84%

Fig. No. 1: Mode of Delivery Distribution

This section presents data on the type of childbirth experienced by the participants. The majority of deliveries were Caesarean (84%), while only 16% were normal deliveries, highlighting a significant prevalence of surgical births.

Table No. 4: Gender Breakdown of Children

Gender	No. of Persons (n=230)	Percentage (%)
Male	116	50%
Female	114	50%

Male
Female

Fig. No. 2: Gender Breakdown of children

The Gender Breakdown of children born to the studied population is evenly split, with 50% male and 50% female, indicating no gender disparity in the sample.

Age (years)	N	%	N	%	N	%
<1	23	10	14	12	9	8
1	42	18	21	18	21	18
2	69	30	33	28	36	32
3	47	20	25	22	22	19
4	33	14	15	13	18	16
5	14	6	7	6	7	6
6	2	1	1	1	1	1

Table No. 5: Age-wise Distribution of Children

No. of child	Male	Female

Fig. No. 3: Age-wise Distribution of children

This section categorizes children based on their age, ranging from under one year to six years. The majority of children fall between 1 to 3 years, with the mean age being 2.37 ± 1.40 years.

Table No. 6: Maternal Age at the time of Pregnancy

18-20	33	14%
21-23	84	37%
24-26	83	36%
27-29	16	7%
30-35	12	5%
39	2	1%

Maternal age (years)	No. of Persons (n=230)	Percentage (%)

Mean± SD is 24.13±3.31

Fig. No. 4: Maternal Age at the Time of Pregnancy

This section details the age distribution of pregnant women, with most between 21-26 years. The mean maternal age is 24.13±3.31 years, showing that the majority of pregnancies occur in the early-to-mid-twenties.

Table No. 7: Pregnancy-Related Health Conditions

Health Conditions	No. of Persons (n=230)	Percentage (%)
Hydramnious	11	5%
Gestational diabetes	13	6%
Preterm delivery	15	7%
Eclampsia	16	7%
Thyroid during pregnancy	17	7%
Gestational BP	21	9%
Miscarriage	25	11%
Pregnancy under 18	29	13%
Anaemia	38	17%
Nil (No complications)	70	30%

Fig. No. 5: Pregnancy-Related Health Conditions

This table highlights various health conditions experienced during pregnancy, such as anemia (17%), pregnancy under 18 years (13%), and miscarriage (11%), among others. A significant portion (30%) reported no complications.

Hole in Heart	1	0.4%
CDH surgery	1	0.4%
Premature	1	0.4%
Asthma	2	1%
Obesity	4	2%
Thyroid	4	2%
Diarrhoea	8	3%
Constipation	8	3%
Nausea/ vomiting	14	6%
Under weight	17	7%
Allergies	20	9%
Nil (No complications)	148	64%

Table No. 8: Health Issues Among Children

Diagnosis	No. of Persons (n=230)	Percentage (%)
Cognitive development	1	0.4%
Weak and No vision	1	0.4%

Fig. No. 6: Health Issues Among Children

This section outlines various health Issues Among children, including allergies (9%), underweight

issues (7%), and nausea/vomiting (6%). However, 64% of children had no reported health issues.

Table No. 9: Educational Background of Mothers

Education	No. of Persons (n=230)	Percentage (%)
PG	1	0.4%
Others	6	3%
Degree	31	13%
Illiterate	40	17%
Intermediate	44	19%
SSC	108	47%

Fig. No. 7: Educational Background of Mothers

The education level of mothers is presented, with the majority (47%) having completed SSC (Secondary School Certificate), while 17% were illiterate, indicating variations in maternal educational attainment.

Table No. 10: Child Growth Patterns

Age (years)	Severe under weight		Moderate under weight		Normal		Obesity		P value
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	
<1	8	28	6	12	12	12	0	0	0.0013*
1	3	10	6	12	19	19	4	8	
2	6	21	7	14	17	17	23	46	
3	4	14	12	24	14	14	10	20	
4	3	10	9	18	16	16	9	18	
5	5	17	10	20	20	20	4	8	

Chi square test was done. Statistically significant difference was found

Fig. No. 8: Growth and Nutritional Status of Children

This section categorizes children into severe underweight, moderate underweight, normal weight, and obesity. A statistically significant difference ($p=0.0013$) was found in child growth distribution.

Table No. 11: Maternal Nutritional Deficiencies

Nutrition	No. of Persons	Percentage (%)
Folic Acid	23	10%
Vitamin B ₁₂	16	7%
Iron	22	10%
Zinc	11	5%
Magnesium	12	5%
Protein	14	6%
Vitamin D	17	7%
Omega-3 fatty acids	15	7%
Chromium	2	1%
Calcium	17	7%
Vitamin B ₆	3	1%
Iodine	8	3%
Selenium	4	2%
Vitamin C	9	4%
Potassium	3	1%
Copper	9	4%
Nil (No complications)	70	30%

Fig No. 9: Maternal Nutritional Deficiencies

This section identifies common nutritional deficiencies in mothers, including iron (10%), folic acid (10%), and vitamin D (7%). Interestingly, 30% of mothers had no reported deficiencies.

DISCUSSION

Maternal nutrition is a critical determinant of both maternal and child health outcomes. The findings of this study highlight significant aspects of maternal nutrition, delivery methods, child health, and associated nutritional deficiencies. One of the key observations from the study is the high prevalence of Caesarean deliveries (84%), which could be attributed to multiple factors such as medical conditions, nutritional deficiencies, or healthcare practices. The mode of delivery has long-term implications for both mother and child, influencing neonatal health, immunity, and metabolic programming. The study also revealed a balanced gender distribution (50% male and 50% female), ensuring that the findings apply equally across both sexes. However, the distribution of child age groups highlights a critical period of development, with a mean age of 2.37 years. This period is essential for cognitive and physical

growth, emphasizing the need for adequate nutrition. Pregnancy-related health conditions such as anemia (17%), pregnancy under 18 years (13%), and miscarriages (11%) indicate gaps in maternal healthcare and nutritional status. These deficiencies can directly impact foetal development, leading to low birth weight, preterm birth, or other complications. The findings related to child health conditions, such as allergies (9%), underweight issues (7%), and nausea/vomiting (6%), further support the argument that maternal nutrition plays a crucial role in postnatal child health. Moreover, maternal education appears to be a significant factor influencing nutritional choices and child health. The majority of mothers had only completed secondary school (47%), while 17% were illiterate. The relationship between education and nutrition awareness directly impacts dietary choices, supplementation practices, and overall healthcare-seeking behavior. Growth assessment among children showed varied results, with cases of severe and moderate underweight prevalent in younger age groups, while obesity was more common in older children. This variation suggests the need for balanced nutritional interventions, as both undernutrition and overnutrition present risks for long-term

health complications. Nutritional deficiencies in mothers, particularly iron (10%), folic acid (10%), and vitamin D (7%), indicate the importance of prenatal supplementation and dietary modifications. Deficiencies in these micronutrients are strongly linked to pregnancy complications, poor birth outcomes, and impaired child growth. Addressing these deficiencies through targeted interventions could significantly improve both maternal and child health. Overall, the findings highlight the importance of maternal nutrition not only for pregnancy outcomes but also for the long-term health of children. Addressing nutritional deficiencies, improving education on maternal health, and implementing targeted healthcare interventions could lead to better health outcomes and reduce the burden of childhood diseases linked to poor maternal nutrition.

CONCLUSION

This study underscores the significant impact of maternal nutrition on pregnancy outcomes, child growth, and overall health. The high rate of Caesarean deliveries suggests potential concerns related to maternal health and nutrition, which need further investigation. The findings related to pregnancy-related health issues, including anemia, early pregnancy, and miscarriages, emphasize the necessity of improving prenatal nutrition and healthcare access. The nutritional status of mothers is a critical determinant of child health, as seen in the prevalence of deficiencies such as iron, folic acid, and vitamin D. These deficiencies not only increase the risk of pregnancy complications but also contribute to issues such as low birth weight, developmental delays, and weakened immunity in children. Ensuring adequate maternal nutrition through proper diet, supplementation, and education can play a crucial role in reducing these risks. Additionally, the findings indicate that both undernutrition and overnutrition are

present among children, highlighting the importance of balanced nutritional interventions. While some children suffer from growth retardation due to undernutrition, others face risks of obesity due to improper dietary habits. This dual burden of malnutrition necessitates targeted programs that promote healthy eating habits from early childhood. Furthermore, maternal education was identified as a key factor influencing nutritional choices and child health outcomes. Educating mothers about proper nutrition, supplementation, and healthcare practices can significantly improve both maternal and child health. Policies aimed at increasing awareness, improving healthcare access, and addressing food security issues could contribute to better maternal and child health indicators.

REFERENCES

1. Cetin I, Mando C, Calabrese S. Maternal predictors of intrauterine growth restriction *curr opin clin Nutr metab care* 2013;16 (3): 310-9.
2. Balasubramanian Sc, Deosthale YG, Kakkar Rk, editors, *Nutritive value of Indian foods*, Hyderabad: National institute of nutrition; 2024.
3. Zhang P, Wu J, Xun N. Role of maternal Nutrition in the Health Outcomes of Mothers and Their Children: A Retrospective Analysis, *Med Sci Monit*, 2019;25;4430-4437.
4. Duggan MB. Nutritional update: relevance to maternal and child health in East Africa. *Afr Health Sci.*2003;3(3):136-143.
5. Ramakrishnan U, Imhoff-Kunsch B, Martorell R, *Maternal nutrition interventions to improve maternal, newborn, and child health outcomes.* Nestle Nutr Inst Workshop Ser. 2014;78:71-80.
6. Martin-Gronert MS, Ozanne SE, *Maternal nutrition during pregnancy and health of the*

- offspring, *Biochem Soc Trans.* 2006;94(Pt 5):779-782.
7. Jouanne M, Oddoux S, Noel A, Voisin- Chiret AS: Nutrient requirements during pregnancy and lactation, *Nutrients.* 2021 13:692.10.3390/nu13020692.
 8. Molloy AM, Kirke PN, Brody LC, Scott JM, Mills JL: Effects of folate and Vitamin B12 deficiencies during pregnancy on foetal, infant, and child development, *Food Nutr Bull.* 2008,29:S101-11; discussion S112-5, 10.1177/15648265080292S114.
 9. McPartlin J, Halligan A, Scott JM, Darling M, Weir DG: Accelerated folate breakdown in pregnancy, *Lancet.* 1993, 341:148-9.10.1016/D140-6736(93) 90007-4.
 10. Casanueva E, Pfeffer F, Drijanski A, Fernandez-Gaxiola AC, Gutierrez-Valenzuela V, Rothenberg SJ: Iron and folate status before pregnancy and anaemia during pregnancy. *ANN Nutr Metab,* 2003, 47:60-3. 10.115/000069276.
 11. Raut AK, Hiwale KM: Iron deficiency anaemia in pregnancy, *Cureus,* 2022, 14:e28918, 10.7759/cureus,28918.
 12. Merz LE, Achebe MO: Iron deficiency in pregnancy: a health inequity. *Am j Clin Nutr.* 2023, 117:1059-60. 10.1.16/j.ajcnut.2023,04.024.
 13. Zhang H, Wang S, Tuo L, Zhai Q, Cui 1, Chen D, Xu D; Relationship between maternal vitamin D levels and adverse outcomes, *Nutrients.* 2022, 14:4230, 10.3390/nu1-4204230.
 14. Tahsin T, Khanam R, Chowdhury NH, et al, Vitamin D deficiency in pregnancy and the risk of preterm birth: a nested case-control study. *BMC pregnancy child birth.* 2023,23:322. 10.1186/s12884-023-05636-z.
 15. Wagner CL, Hollis BW: The implications of vitamin D status during pregnancy on mother and her developing child, *Front Endocrinol (Lausanne),* 2018, 9:500. 10.3389/fendo.2018.00500.
 16. Dunphy L, Tang AW: Vitamin (B12) deficiency presenting with a pancytopenia in pregnancy. *BMJ Case Rep.* 2023, 16:e249955, 10.1136/bcr-2022-249955.
 17. He J, Jiang D, Cul X, Ji c: Vitamin B12 status and folic acid / vitamin B12 related to the risk of gestational diabetes mellitus in pregnancy: a systematic review and meta-analysis of observational studies, *BMC pregnancy child birth,* 2022, 22:587, 10.1186/s12884-022-04911-9.
 18. Machamba AA, Azevedo FM, Fracalossi KO, do CC Franceschini S: Effect of iodine supplementation in pregnancy on neurocognitive development on offspring in iodine deficiency areas: a systematic review, *Arch Endocrinol Metab.* 2021, 65:352-67. 10.20945/2359-3997000000376.
 19. Branstetter AL, Garthus-Nie gel S, Brandlistuen RE, Caspersen IH, Meltzer HM, Abel MH: Mild-to-moderate iodine deficiency and symptoms of emotional distress and depression in pregnancy and six months postpartum- results from a large pregnancy cohort. *J Affect Disord.* 2022, 318:347-56. 10.1016/j.jad.2022.09.009.

HOW TO CITE: Dr. Shaik Farahan Subahan*, Dr. J. N. Suresh Kumar, Chimata Hanumantha Rao, Chuppana Naga Veera Durga Sai Madhurya, Dudekula Sajeedha, Gurrapusala Lakshmi Venkata Surekha, Sheik Nageena Bee, Community based Retrospective Study on Impact of Maternal Nutrition and Child health outcomes in Yallamanda & Nearby Villages of Narasaraopet, *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.*, 2025, Vol 3, Issue 3, 3353-3366 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15112837>

